

PROBLEMS OF IMPROVEMENT IN IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

Muradov Botir Hayat

Independent applicant of the Department of Industrial Economics and Management, Faculty of Engineering Technologies, Tashkent State Technical University named after I.A. Karimova

doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11300084

Abstract. This article analyzes the methodological aspects of evaluating the efficiency of innovative management of enterprises based on the systematic analysis of the efficiency indicators of industrial enterprises. The article also presents the factors affecting the efficiency of innovative management of industrial enterprises, based on grouping them according to the spheres of influence, a scientific proposal and practical recommendations aimed at increasing the efficiency of innovative management of industrial enterprises have been developed.

Key words: efficiency, innovative management, scientific research, innovative costs, innovative product, innovative activity, innovative management effectiveness.

In the process of institutional reforms carried out in Uzbekistan since the first years of independence, a system of improving and supporting industrial enterprises in accordance with the principles of market economy relations was formed. In a relatively short period of time, the legal bases and organizational-economic mechanisms necessary for the regulation and management of activities in the field of industrial enterprises of the economy were established. As a result, in recent years, stable growth rates have been observed in the sector of industrial enterprises of our country's economy. In addition, the experience of developed countries in the world shows that the widespread introduction of innovations in the economy increases international competitiveness and creates a solid foundation for sustainable development. In particular, the widespread implementation of innovative activities in industrial enterprises has a significant impact on the increase in the economic efficiency of the industry. This situation is clearly demonstrated by the correlation between the level of innovative development and the competitiveness of the industrial sector. the international innovation index, "among the economically developed countries, such countries as Germany (2.26 points), USA (1.80 points), Japan (1.79 points) and Sweden (1.64 points) are leading is doing According to the Bloomberg Agency's research, in 2024, the countries of South Korea, Germany, Finland, and Switzerland occupy the highest place in the ranking of the world's innovative economy. In turn, the development of innovations ensures the high efficiency of industrial enterprises in these countries. Modernization of the national economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan

depends primarily on the efficient use of human resources. The study of the human factor reveals its content and essence as a resource, both qualitatively and quantitatively. Improving the economy of our country, as well as solving a number of socioeconomic tasks before us, requires effective use of human resources. The dependence of the economy on human potential is increasing more and more, it is oriented towards meeting its needs, the direction of intangible values, spiritual and cultural needs in its composition is changing. Today, the content of social development is changing - the importance and contribution of its intellectual, spiritual and cultural components is increasing. In this regard, the Decree No. PF-60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" contains the following: "In the following years, based on the principle of "For human dignity", further increasing the well-being of our people, transformation of economic sectors and rapid development of entrepreneurship, unconditionally ensuring human rights and interests, based on the in-depth analysis of complex global processes and the results of our country's progress and in order to determine the priorities of reforms aimed at forming an active civil society: building a people-friendly state by increasing human dignity and further developing a free civil society; making the principles of justice and the rule of law the most basic and necessary condition for development in our country; rapid development of the national economy and ensuring high growth rates; conducting a fair social policy, developing human capital; ensuring spiritual development and bringing the industry to a new level; approach universal problems based on national interests; strengthening the security and defense potential of our country, conducting an open, pragmatic and active foreign policy. The capitalization of the human factor and the formation of social capital directly depend on the ability of individuals and communities to absorb innovations, perceive and stimulate innovation. Changing the leading technological order and forming a class of new public identities is impossible without changing the leading anthropological model to achieve the future of the country and the nation in the global situation. Human potential is a complex and understudied topic. Currently, there is no clear understanding of what human potential is. There are different interpretations about its essence, structural elements and its relationship with "human capital", "labor potential", "human potential" and other concepts. Human potential (in the general sense) is the ability to demonstrate in practice the theoretical capabilities of a person (person) or humanity (persons). In many literatures, the concept of "human potential" is given as the concepts of "human factor" and "human capital". In particular, human potential is often confused with "human capital". The phenomenology of the systematic nature of human potential has the following characteristics: 1) consistency: human potential has systematic properties and cannot be reduced to a simple sum of the list of human qualities; 2) external

conditionality: for the formation and realization of human potential, "external" conditions and factors to it, the nature of the environment of its existence, as a rule, are of decisive importance; 3) transparency: human potential is characterized by the presence of hidden characteristics, which can manifest themselves when certain conditions change. 4) strategic: the characteristics of human potential determine the possibilities of human development both in the near future and in the long term. To date, there are no single methodological studies on the understanding of human potential, fundamental research of existing terminology and classification of concepts, indicators of normative assessment of the quality of human potential. In the methodological and conceptual justification and interpretation of the concept of human potential, the system of indicators of human potential has not yet been developed, especially as a comprehensive indicator of the level of economic efficiency improvement in industrial enterprises. Also, the comparative assessment of the quality of human potential in industrial enterprises and the methodical analysis of the factors of reducing human potential have not been fully implemented. Today, it is necessary to develop activities in a manner that integrates human potential, its principles and directions. In Uzbekistan, attention is being paid to the rapid development of the leading sectors of the economy, including the industrial sector. Great efforts are being made to equip industrial enterprises with high-level modern equipment and technologies, and to implement them in production, to transition to an innovative economy. In this regard, " ...the most important guarantee of sustainable economic growth is the production of competitive products, finding new international markets for them and increasing exports, making full use of the transit potential. " 2. In order to solve these tasks, deepening scientific research in areas such as increasing innovative activity in the industrial production system, determining the trends and priority directions of innovative-investment activities, evaluating the effectiveness of innovative projects, improving the financial mechanism of implementing innovative activities in enterprises is of particular importance. PF-4947 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017" On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan ", PF-5264 dated November 29, 2017" On the Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" on the establishment" , No. PF-5308 of January 22, 2018 " On the state program on the implementation of the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 " decrees, the decision of May 7, 2018 No. PQ-3698 "On additional measures to improve the mechanisms of introducing innovations into economic sectors and sectors " and the tasks specified in other regulatory legal documents related to this field serves to a certain extent in implementation. In the conditions of the increasingly developing market economy,

improving the indicators of national and international competitiveness of enterprises requires that their economic activities be carried out in an innovative direction. In the following years, the development of innovative management of industrial enterprises in our country will be one of the priorities of the reforms being implemented. In particular, "by 2030, it is planned to include Uzbekistan among the TOP-50 countries in the Global Innovation Index." In order to achieve this goal, the priority task of improving the country's position on the low indicators recorded in this index is defined in the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026. This situation arouses the need to conduct researches of scientific and practical importance aimed at increasing the efficiency of innovative management of industrial enterprises in our country. Effective implementation of innovative activities in economic sectors is the main support of the democratic reforms being carried out in our republic at the modern stage. In particular, in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. PF-60 "On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", the main social and economic development of our country one of the priority tasks is to continue the industrial policy aimed at ensuring the stability of the national economy and increasing the share of industry in the gross domestic product, and increasing the production volume of industrial products by 1.4 times. Also, the tasks of developing and implementing industrial concepts in the "Innovative Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-165 dated July 6, 2022 one of the main directions and goals is to ensure rapid socioeconomic growth of regions by increasing the innovative activity of small businesses. Based on the fair policy conducted by the head of our state, in order to rationally satisfy the growing economic needs with limited resources, it is necessary to fundamentally improve the management mechanism of enterprises operating in industrial sectors, to increase the volume and quality of production based on innovative ideas, these priority tasks are national means the urgency of researching the mechanism of innovative management in economic sectors, including industrial enterprises. Typically, firms engaged in the extraction and production of raw materials outsource the least profitable sector, while firms providing product design and aftersales service absorb most of the economic benefits. In particular, factories in Indonesia, which is considered a supplier of raw materials for the production of various brands of sports shoes, receive 20-25% of the income from the sale of finished products. According to the analysis, today some market economies are forming and developing countries have launched the production of high-tech innovative products in the enterprises of the processing industry, while some are giving priority to the technical-technological arming of the raw material production sectors. These countries lag significantly behind developed countries in terms of sales of high-

tech innovative products in international trade. The raw materials and semifinished products produced in them are processed by the industrially developed countries and come back to them as finished products. This situation indicates that the state of innovative management of industrial enterprises and its low level of development is one of the factors that have a direct negative impact on the country's economy. In particular, as a result of processing the data obtained from enterprises operating in our country, the volume of products produced per capita of hired workers in enterprises that have implemented product innovations in recent years in our country is on average 12 million soums compared to enterprises that have not implemented innovations. It was found that production increased by 26 million soums in enterprises that introduced innovations, 19 million soums in enterprises that adopted external knowledge, and 44 million soums due to the effective use of internal and external opportunities in the implementation of innovations. This situation indicates that the economic efficiency indicator is significantly higher in enterprises with innovative management practices compared to enterprises with traditional management. According to the analysis of the specific features of the organization of innovative management in the industrial sectors of the national economy, as the scale of the enterprise engaged in innovative activity increases, its innovative activity increases accordingly. According to statistics, in recent years, 28% of small enterprises, 30% of medium-sized enterprises, and 32% of large enterprises operating in the branches of the national economy of our country have introduced product innovations into their practices, while those related to management innovations accounted for 14 percent in small enterprises, 19 percent in medium-sized enterprises, and 22 percent in large enterprises. Based on this, the low level of innovative activity in the industrial enterprises of our national economy and the high share of low-tech industries are the reasons why it occupies the lower places in the international world rankings that assess the innovative activity in the current economy. In particular, according to the data obtained from the national statistical database, by the end of 2024, the share of the high-tech sector in the composition of industrial sectors will be 2.1% (2.7% in 2023). 23.2% (20.2) of medium -high technology, 36.4% (39.7%) of medium-low technology, and 38.3% (37.2) of low-tech industry. By the end of 2023, according to the Global Innovation Index rating developed for the countries of the world, Switzerland, the USA, Sweden, Great Britain and the Kingdom of the Netherlands will lead the list of countries whose economies have introduced innovative activity. According to this index, Uzbekistan took 82nd place with a score of 25.3, and was included in the third place among the countries of Central and South Asia after India and Iran. Based on our researches, it means that there is a need to prioritize the development of the practice of innovative management of industrial enterprises in our country, including increasing their innovative activity. In the state policy aimed at

ensuring the stability of the economic growth of the countries of the world, mainly by implementing innovative projects in the management of enterprises in industrial sectors, creating new consumer values, ensuring production efficiency, their financial stability, as well as the national economy and the economy of foreign countries with the focus on increasing global competitiveness and development index indicators. This leads to an increase in the quality of production, an increase in the source of income and a further increase in purchasing power According to the analysis of the world practice of developing the practice of innovative management of industrial enterprises, it is innovation that is considered as an important factor for ensuring sustainable economic growth today.

References

1. B.X. Muradov. Ko‘mir sanoati korxonalarini rivojlantirishning tashkiliy iqtisodiy mexanizmlarining samaradordik ko‘rsatkichlari va ularni baholash. 2022/4/22. proceedings of the conference 2-international scientific and scientific-technical conference «problems and prospects of innovative technique and technology in agri-food chain» Part 2. Stranitsi 554-557.

2. B.X. Muradov. Raqamli iqtisodiyotda ko‘mir qazib olish sanoati korxonalarining strategik boshqarish mexanizmlari. International conference on learning and teaching. Tom 1. Stranitsi 515-521. Polucheno s <https://researchedu.org/index.-php/ict/article/view/2028>.

3. Б.Х. Мурадов. Роль телекоммуникационных технологий и развитие механизмов индустриальной экономики в отрасли энергоресурсов для добычи угля. Грузинские ученые, том 4.(4) 13 августа 2022, Страница 215–219. <https://doi.org/10.52340/gS.2022.04.04.24>.

4. B.X. Muradov. Makro va mikroiqtisodiyotining sanoat korxonalarini tashkiliy iqtisodiy mexanizmlarning rivojlanishida ekologiyani o‘rni kerakmi?"Роль инновационных методов и технологий в обеспечении экологической устойчивости" международный научный и научно-технический Собрание Сборник. том 1. Страница 161-166. 2022/9/11. Ташкент г.

5. Б.Х. Мурадов. Экономическое развитие факторов, которые влияют на формирование управление механизма промышленных предприятий на анализ действующей политики информационной безопасности. Научный импульс. Россия. Москва г. том 1. (3), Страница 699–706.

6. Б.Х. Мурадов. Совершенствование организационно-экономических механизмов развития промышленных предприятий и факторы повышения конкурентоспособности в условиях глобализации. "Moliya bozorini rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari, zamonaviy tendensiyalari va istiqbollari"

mavzusidagi Respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi. Toshkent sh. 2022/11/25. Страницы 177-179.

7. Б.Х. Мурадов. Совершенствование организационно-экономических механизмов развитие с инноваций как основа конкурентной стратегии промышленных предприятий. "Moliya bozorini rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari, zamonaviy tendensiyalari va istiqbollari" mavzusidagi Respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi. Toshkent sh. 2022/11/25. Страницы 190-193.

8. Б.Х. Мурадов. Стратегический менеджмент как прогрессивное направление организационно-экономических механизмов развития предприятия промышленных предприятий (на примере АО «Ўзбеккўмир»). "Moliya bozorini rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari, zamonaviy tendensiyalari va istiqbollari" mavzusidagi Respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi. Toshkent sh. 2022/11/25. Страницы 180-183.